

Development And Validation of Uv Spectrophotometry for Imeglimin Hcl Using Green Analytical Chemistry Approach

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for novel analytical methods for recently developed drugs necessitates the development of simple, accurate, and environmentally sustainable approaches. This research was undertaken to develop and validate a UV-visible spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Imeglimin Hydrochloride, a new antidiabetic agent, using methanol as a solvent in accordance with Green Analytical Chemistry principles. The method was designed to be straightforward and cost-effective, suitable for routine quality control. Spectrophotometric analysis was conducted at 245 nm, and the method was validated following ICH guidelines, assessing parameters such as linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantitation (LOQ). The method demonstrated excellent linearity within the concentration range of 2–10 µg/mL with a correlation coefficient close to 1. Precision and accuracy results were within acceptable limits, indicating the reliability of the method. The LOD and LOQ values confirmed the method's sensitivity, and assay results for marketed tablet formulations verified its practical applicability. Green assessment was performed by using AGREE software and the score was 0.77 which indicates that the developed method is eco-friendly. The study successfully developed a validated, green, and robust method for the estimation of Imeglimin Hydrochloride, providing a sustainable tool for pharmaceutical analysis.

Keywords: Imeglimin HCl, UV Spectrophotometry, Validation, Green Analytical Chemistry, AGREE

INTRODUCTION

Imeglimin HCl is a novel oral agent for the treatment of type 2 diabetes (T2D). Imeglimin hydrochloride is the "first drug of a new class of glimins. Imeglimin hydrochloride is a tetrahydro triazine compound with a chemical name of (6R)-(+)-4- dimethylamino-2-imino-6-methyl-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine hydrochloride. With a molecular formula of C₆H₁₄CIN₅ and a weight of 191.66 g/mol.

It has a Dual Effects: Imeglimin hydrochloride mechanism of action involves two key actions:

a) Amplification of Glucose-Stimulated Insulin Secretion (GSIS): Imeglimin hydrochloride enhances the release of insulin from the pancreas in response to elevated blood glucose levels.

b) Enhanced Insulin Action: Imeglimin hydrochloride improves insulin sensitivity, potentially by inhibiting hepatic glucose output and improving insulin signalling in both liver and skeletal muscle.[1]

Fig .1: Chemical structure of Imeglimin hydrochloride

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Among the various methods available for the determination of drugs, spectrophotometry. Continues to be very popular, because of their simplicity, specificity, and low cost. This study presents a new spectrophotometric method for the determination of imeglimin hydrochloride by using methanol as a solvent in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation. Accordingly, the objective of this study was to develop and validate the UV-spectrophotometric method for the estimation of imeglimin hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations as per ICH guidelines by using methanol as solvent and to develop a green analytical approach method.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Reagents and materials:

I) Imeglimin hydrochloride

II) Methanol

Preparation of solution:

- Preparation of standard solution:

A precisely measured quantity of Imeglimin Hydrochloride 100mg, was transferred to a

volumetric flask of 100 ml. It was then dissolved in methanol and the volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent. This yielded with a solution containing 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of Imeglimin hydrochloride.

- Preparation of stock solution:

From the above solution 10 ml was pipetted out and transferred into a volumetric flask of 100 ml. The final volume was made using methanol to produce a standard solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Further dilutions were prepared using these stock solutions.

Selection of wavelength for analysis of imeglimin hydrochloride:

Appropriate volume 1 ml of standard stock solution of imeglimin hydrochloride was Transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to a mark with methanol to give Concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The resulting solution was scanned in the UV range (200–400nm). In spectrum imeglimin hydrochloride showed absorbance maximum at 245 nm. [Figure 2].

Fig 2: UV spectrum of Imeglimin hydrochloride at 245 nm

Validation of the method:

The method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy and precision.

Linearity study

The linearity response was determined by analyzing at five independent levels of calibration curve in the range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for Imeglimin hydrochloride at

2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 µg/mL. The linearity response was recorded five times (n=5). The calibration curve was then plotted as Absorbance v/s Concentration. Correlation coefficient and regression line equations were calculated using MS-Excel.

Accuracy:

To the reanalysed sample solution a known amount of standard stock solution was added at different level (0%, 80%, 100% and 120%). The solution were reanalysed by proposed method.

Precision:

Precision of method was studied as repeatability, intraday and interday. Repeatability was determined by analysing 6 µg/mL concentration of Imeglimin hydrochloride solution for six time. Intraday precision was determined by analysing 6 µg/mL concentration of Imeglimin hydrochloride solution for three times in a day at short time intervals, i.e. in the morning, afternoon and evening. Interday precision was determined by analysing 6 µg/mL concentration of Imeglimin hydrochloride solution three times in three different consecutive days.

Sensitivity:

The sensitivity of measurement of Imeglimin hydrochloride by the use of proposed method was estimated in terms of the limit of quantification (LOQ) and limit of detection (LOD). The LOQ and LOD were calculated using equation $LOD = 3.3 \times S.D./Slope$ and $LOQ = 10 \times S.D./Slope$ where S.D. is standard deviation of the peak area of drug and slope is slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

Application of the proposed method for pharmaceutical formulation:

For analysis of commercial formulation 500mg Imeglimin hydrochloride tablet (Imextor) was taken. The tablet powder equivalent to 500 mg of Imeglimin hydrochloride was accurately weighed and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. A 5 ml volume of methanol was added and the flask was sonicated for 10 min. The volume was made up to 10 ml with methanol mixed well and filtered through Whatman paper no. 41. An aliquot of 1 ml of this solution was

transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 10 ml with methanol. Further 1 ml of this solution was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to mark with methanol. Analyse the solution and record the mean absorbance and % label claim obtained.

Green Analytical Chemistry Evaluation- AGREE:

The principles of green chemistry are increasingly integrated into diverse research endeavours to educate scientists about the environmental implication of their work. Similarly these principles are now permeating the field of analytical chemistry, influencing both instrumentation and analytical methodologies. The resulting method undergoes assessment through evaluation and tool metrics. Software applications like AGREE are employed for the purpose of evaluating the adherence to green chemistry principle.

AGREE- Analytical GREEnness calculator

It's free software developed to evaluate how green analytical chemistry methods, based on the 12 Principles of Green Analytical Chemistry (GAC). Help scientists design or choose methods that are safer, cleaner, more efficient, and more environmentally friendly.

Each of the 12 principles is scored from 0 (bad) to 1 (good). The software combines the results into a final overall score (also between 0 and 1). A circular diagram (like a clock) with 12 slices representing each principle. The colour ranges from red (poor) to green (excellent).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Method validation

The proposed method was validated as per ICH guideline. The solution of the drug were prepared as per the earlier adopted procedure given in experiment.

Linearity studies

The linear regression data for the calibration curves showed good linear relationship over the concentration range 2-10 µg/mL for Imeglimin hydrochloride [Fig.3]. Linear regression equation was

found to be $Y=0.0682x+0.1243$ ($r^2=0.9728$). The result is expressed in [Table.1]

Fig no.3: Calibration curve of Imeglimin hydrochloride

Table 1: Linearity study of Imeglimin hydrochloride

Sr No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Mean absorbance \pm STD (n=7)	% RSD
1	2	0.304 \pm 0.003	0.854
2	4	0.342 \pm 0.006	1.866
3	6	0.524 \pm 0.002	0.367
4	8	0.680 \pm 0.007	1.053
5	10	0.818 \pm 0.012	1.415

Accuracy:

which showed that the % amount found was between 98.87 -100.61.

The solution were reanalysed by the proposed method ; results of recovery studies are reported in Table 2

Table 2: Result of recovery study for Imeglimin hydrochloride

Level	Amt. of table t eqt.	Amt. of std. spiked (mg)	Absorbance	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Dilution factor	Amt. of drug (μg)	Amt. of drug (mg)	Amt. recovered	% Recovery
0%	500	0	0.204	1.927	250000	481770.8	481.77		
0%	500				250000				
0%	500				250000				
80%	500	400	0.326	3.521	250000	880330.7	880.33	398.56	98.87
80%	500				250000				
80%	500				250000				
100%	500	500	0.357	3.924	250000	981135.6	981.13	499.33	99.17
100%	500				250000				
100%	500				250000				
120%	500	600	0.388	4.326	250000	1081654.7	108.16	108.16	100.61
120%	500				250000				
120%	500				250000				

Precision:

The precision of the developed method was expressed in terms of % relative standard deviation (%RSD). These results show reproducibility of the

assay. The %RSD value found to be less than 2 that indicate that this method precise [Table 3].

- **Repeatability:**

Table 3: Result of repeatability of sample

Drug(6µg/mL)	Wavelength	Mean absorbance ± STD (n=7)	% RSD
IME	245	0.5248 ± 0.0024	0.4592

- **Intraday precision:**

Table 4: Result of Intraday

Concentration (µg/mL)	Wavelength	Mean absorbance ± STD (n=3)	% RSD
6	245	0.528± 0.001	0.189

- **Interday precision**

Table 5: Result of Interday

Concentration(µg/m)	Wavelength	Mean absorbance ± STD (n=3)	% RSD
6	245q	0.526±0.003	0.570

Sensitivity:

The linearity equation was found to be $Y=0.0682x+0.1243$. The LOQ and LOD for Imeglimin hydrochloride were found to be 0.08593 and 0.2641 respectively. *Application of the proposed method for pharmaceutical formulation:*

The spectrum was recorded at 245nm. The concentration of drug were calculated from the linear regression equation. The % amount found was 98.35%.

Table 6: Assay of Tablet formulation

Brand name of tablet	Label claim of tablet(mg)	Amt. of imeglimin found (mg)	% Amt. found
Imextor	500	481.77	96.35

Fig 4: Marketed formulation

Green Analytical Chemistry Evaluation- AGREE Software:

Optimized method data were entered in the 12 principles of AGREE to evaluate the eco-friendly nature of the method.

I) Sampling procedure: In field sampling and direct analysis

II) Amount of sample: 2 ml

III) Positioning of analytical device: On-line

IV) Process involved in sample preparation: Fewer

V) Semi-automatic method and sample preparation is miniaturized

VI) No derivatization of drug

VII) Amount of waste: 2 ml

VIII) One analyte determined in single run and 3 sample analysed per hour

IX) Total power consumption: 0.013 kWh

X) Reagent used is bio based

XI) No toxic reagent used

XII) Threat which is not avoided is methanol is flammable. The final value received from AGREE software is 0.77 which indicates the method is eco-friendly. A value closer to one indicates the method greenness.

Fig 5: AGREE Score

CONCLUSION AND SUMMARY

A simple, specific, accurate, precise and eco-friendly UV spectroscopy method has been developed and validated for estimation of Imeglimin hydrochloride. The method was able to estimate Imeglimin hydrochloride accurately by using methanol as a solvent. The method was validated as per ICH (Q2 R1) guidelines. Evaluation using green analytical tool like AGREE indicates highly favourable eco-friendly outcomes.

SUMMARY

Numbers of methods of UV spectrophotometry have been reported for estimation of Imeglimin hydrochloride, an anti-diabetic drug using distilled water as a solvent. No reported estimation method for Imeglimin hydrochloride was found using Methanol as a solvent. A specific, accurate, precise and eco-friendly method has been developed for the estimation of Imeglimin hydrochloride by using Methanol as a solvent. The linear regression analysis data for the calibration plots showed a good linear relationship with $R^2 = 0.9971$ in the concentration range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Imeglimin hydrochloride. Recovery of drugs was achieved 99.55% by developed method.

Limit of detection and limit of quantitation were found to be 0.08593 and 0.2641 respectively. Method was applied for estimation of Imeglimin hydrochloride in tablets. The content of Imeglimin hydrochloride marketed formulations was found to be 96.35% of labelled amount. The green analytical chemistry metric was performed using AGREE software and the score was 0.77 based on its 12 principles. Which depicts that the developed method was eco-friendly.

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